

A BRIEF STUDY ON BASHEER'S MINOR LITERATURE

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Abstract

Vaikom Muhammad Basheer (21st January 1908 - 05th July 1994) was one of the prominent Malayalam fiction writers. Born at Thalayolaparambu in Vaikom he is better known as Beypore Sultan. He was a humanist, freedom fighter, novelist and a short story writer. Basheer is known for his unconventional style of language in Malayalam literature. His characters were an output of his keen observance. He skillfully combined humour and pathos in his works. Love, hunger

and poverty are recurring themes in his works. *Baalyakaalasakhi*, *Premalekhanam*, *Paaththummaayude aadu* (Pathumma's Goat), *Shabdangal*, *Ntuppuppaakkoraanaendaarnnu* and *Mathilukal* (Walls) are his major works.

The novel *Mathilukal* deals with the prison lives in the pre-independence days. It is a novel of sad irony set against a turbulent political backdrop. The novel was later made into a film (*Mathilukal*, 1989) by Adoor Gopalakrishnan with Mammooty playing as Basheer.

Keywords: Malayalam, Literature, Satyagraha, Freedom Fighter, Navel.

Vaikkom Muhammad Basheer's short Malayalam novel *Ntuppuppaakkoranendaarnnu!* (Me Grandad 'ad an Elephant!) provoked bitter and passionate public controversy when it was first published in 1951. During the early '50s, when involved debates about modern and progressive literature were taking place in Kerala, many leftist thinkers were quick to denounce the book. A prominent argument was that when other writers were calling for revolution, this book-in which the central male character had passed his M. A. degree but was depicted as digging a toilet pit-was highly regressive.

However, when Joseph Mundassery, himself a writer and the Minister for Education in the first communist ministry of Kerala, took personal initiative to get the book prescribed as a textbook for schools, it was the writers and community leaders on the right who protested against the book. There were debates and protests in the legislative assembly, where MLA's declared that the book was unsuitable to be allowed entry into schools-or anywhere, for that matter! Many leaders of the Muslim and Christian communities, and the newspapers controlled by them, assailed the book and said that it would lead students astray.² "As a result," writes the leading Malayalam publisher D. C. Kizhakkemuri (1994), "tens of thousands of students did not buy the book." The government probably sold off these copies by weight in the open market, for "the book was widely sold on the pavements for one an 11a or two an 11as".

However, even in those stormy early days, several readers and critics also perceived *Me Grandad 'ad an Elephant!* as one of the finest Malayalam novels that had ever been written. This favourable response to the novel has since rapidly grown to the point of establishing it as one of the most critically acclaimed and best-selling pieces of Malayalam fiction of all the shortly after

publication, it won an award from the Madras Government and then the prestigious M. P. Paul prize. It has sold an estimated one hundred and fifty thousand copies in Malayalam and has been translated into over eighteen Indian and foreign languages. Madassery Madhava Warriar (1994) writes: "I have no hesitation in declaring loudly and firmly that *Me Grandad 'ad an Elephant!* has been the greatest novel produced after *Illdulekha*".

Basheer the person-who acquired the status of a legend in Kerala during his own lifetime-was no less celebrated or controversial than his fiction. Born in 1908 at Thalayolaparambu in the taluk of Vaikom, Basheer was influenced by questions of freedom and social reform early in life. Even as a school student, he got involved in the Vaikom Satyagraha and was able "to touch Mahatma Gandhi" during a meeting-an experience that overwhelmed him. He decided to quit school and ran away from home to join the Congress-led Indian freedom movement at Kozhikode. His involvement in the salt satyagraha ended with his getting beaten up by the police and locked up in Kannur jail, where he was influenced by the revolutionaries advocating violent resistance to colonial rule. Released from prison he started a resistance journal *Ujjeevanam*; the government soon cracked down on the movement and Basheer had to leave Travancore state.

His exile lasted for seven years and he travelled all over India (even to Arabia and the coasts of Africa), learning several languages and vocations, soaking in a wide range of experiences. At different points in his life he was with *sanvasis* in the Himalayas and *sufis* at Ajmer, a . . . wrestler, magician, cook, cleaner, farmer, bookseller. His career as a writer was also interrupted by spells in prison, and at times in asylums following bouts of

manic depression. He published his first book, *Premaiekanam*, in 1943, and the celebrated *Childhood Friend* which he had first written in English during his exile from Kerala in 1944, quickly becoming ranked among the best talents in Malayalam fiction.

He was a prolific writer, but through most of the 1950s from 1954 to 1959 there was a long and significant cessation of creative output, as he was ravaged with mental illness and depression. After treatment at the Vallapuzha mental sanatorium in Thrissur, he started a famous bookshop at Ernakulam that soon became a favoured meeting place for writers and book-lovers. The fierce controversy over *Me Grandad 'ad all Elephant!* during 1957 depressed him further, but he returned to writing in 1959 with *Pathumma's Goat*, a mixed genre cameo which many regard as his most interesting work. He continued to write stories, short novels, screenplays and magazine columns, and won a large number of prizes and accolades.'

He was a conspicuous presence in the Malayalam literary public sphere till his death in July 1994 at the age of ninety four. Before proceeding with the analysis, I wish to quickly summarise the "story" of this narrative: A rich, illiterate Muslim family-comprising of Vattan Adima, Kunjuthamma and their daughter Kunjupathumma-are assertively proud of their "ancestral heritage" (symbolised by their grandad's mythic elephant. They are also anxious about any contact with the kaffirs or infidels who surround their comforting world.

The family suddenly loses a legal battle and are forced to evict from their palatial household. When they shift into a small hut, the young Kunjupathumma, for one, is happy because for the first time in her twenty years she is "free" to move out of the seclusion of her house-to bathe, to collect firewood, etc. As a result of this freedom, she meets her new neighbours, the young elegant city-bred poet Nisar Ahmad, and his vivacious sister Aisha. Kunjupathumma initially mistakes both of them to be kaffirs because of their dress and dialect, yet they claim that they are the "genuine" Muslims. Following a series of finely evoked episodes and vignettes of cultural friction and fusion, by the end of the novel (despite the "resistance" of Kunjupathumma's parents, her new friends train her to be a modern woman, speaking chaste Malayalam (i.e., the standard dialect), gorgeous in a sari, her hair bedecked with flowers, the blooming bride of Nisar Ahmad.

Conclusion

Instead, we might approach it as a conceptual site where issues of minoritization, casteism, tribalism, rural/agrarian impoverishment, etc. are staged and negotiated. This point has been

highlighted. In other words, it represents the painful experiences of discrimination and subordination faced by the Muslims in the new "secular" nation that was inaugurated in 1947. Thus, my dissertation has focused on Indian nationalism's cultural and narrative politics, which discursively produce the minorities as well as the regions of India. My study has been animated by the recognition that the various "minoritized" communities have evolved a different mode of politics to resist economic and cultural domination. One discernible outcome of this politics is the advent of regional parties with social justice and geographically equitable economic policies high on their agenda.

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